

Interview Questionnaire

Summary of the research: The field of Software Engineering includes working software and the associated defects with that software. Due to the deficiency of modern tools, multiple human-centric issues such as personality, ethnicity, and culture, usage based on diverse age, gender, educational background, etc., are overlooked and creates a gap between customer and maintenance teams. The problem associated with human-centric defects is the difficulty in evaluating and reporting the issue due to its subjective nature. For instance, while booking an Uber, the option to include the child seat is very confusing and requires extra effort from the user side to get it included in their ride. For a regular user, this is not an issue. However, for a parent with a child, this instantly becomes a human-centric defect.

The interview questions are the basis for discussion with the participant and can lead to further interesting insights.

Section 1: Demographics

1. Country of residence:
2. Age:
 - a. <20
 - b. 20-24
 - c. 25-29
 - d. 30-34
 - e. 35-39
 - f. 40-50
 - g. 51-60
 - h. 60+
3. Gender:
 - a. Male
 - b. Female
 - c. Non-binary / gender diverse
 - d. My gender identity isn't listed. I identify as: <<Text>>
 - e. Prefer not to say
4. Highest Education:
 - a. Some high school credit, no diploma, or the equivalent
 - b. High school graduate, diploma, or the equivalent
 - c. Some college credit, no degree
 - d. Trade/technical/vocational training
 - e. Associate degree
 - f. Bachelor's degree
 - g. Master's degree
 - h. Professional degree
 - i. Doctorate degree
 - j. Other: <<Text>>
5. If you are currently a student or have completed a college degree, please specify your field(s) of study:
 - a. Computer Science
 - b. Information Technology
 - c. Computer Engineering

- d. Information Systems
 - e. Architecture
 - f. Arts and Humanities
 - g. Chemical Engineering
 - h. Biology
 - i. Business
 - j. Other: <<Text>>
6. Current Role:
- a. Project Management
 - b. Software Architect
 - c. Software Engineer/Software Developer/Programmer
 - d. Delivery Engineer/Lead
 - e. User interface designer/UX
 - f. Test Engineer/Tester/Quality Assurance
 - g. Security Engineer/Consultant
 - h. Business Analyst
 - i. Operations
 - j. Other: <<Text>>
7. Total Experience:
- a. 0-2 years
 - b. 3-5 years
 - c. 6-8 years
 - d. 9+ years
8. What is your field of work?
- a. Information Technology
 - b. IT-Finance
 - c. IT-Manufacturing
 - d. IT-Spatial
 - e. IT-Government
 - f. IT-Gaming
 - g. IT-Healthcare
 - h. IT-Telecommunications
 - i. Other: <<Text>>

Section 2: Human-centric defects

0. According to you, what is the difference between normal defects and human-centric defects?

1. Have you ever experienced human-centric defects in your projects? If yes, then how did you acknowledge them in the project?

2. Do you use any defect reporting tools such as JIRA, Bugzilla, Trello, etc. in those projects? What are there challenges while reporting human-centric defects? Do you have any suggestions to improve them?

3. Do you think teams or organizations' take human-centric aspects into consideration while designing, developing, and testing software? Please elaborate with examples.

4. According to you, do developers' positive or negative emotions plays important role in fixing human-centric defects?
Can a positive team climate make the fixing of human-centric defects faster?

5. As culture/language can have a significant effect on how people interpret a situation and react to it. According to you, how does it impacts on reporting and fixing of human-centric defects?

6. In your experience, what factors contribute while assigning developers to a defect?

7. Can previous defect history such as comments, commits, developer's knowledge can help solve human-centric defects faster?

8. Do you think the lack of taxonomy is the primary reason nobody has heard about human-centric defects or encountered them?

9. If we to create a taxonomy or triage such human-centric defects, what do you think the important things included in that?

10. Do you have any other suggestions on how to improve reporting and fixing of human-centric issues?